

Synthesis and Mass Spectra of Substituted Phenylethylamines and their Schiff Bases[†]

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Manuscript received 15 November 1985, revised 22 July 1986, accepted 9 March 1987

Substituted phenylethylamine (4-10) and their Schiff bases (11-17) have been synthesised. A comparative study of the positive and negative ion mass spectra of 4-10 and 11-17 has been made. The results have shown that positive ion chemical ionisation is more diagnostic for the identification of 4-10 whereas positive ion electron impact is preferable for 11-17. The fragmentation modes of these compounds have been established with the help of exact mass measurements and metastable ion data.

SUBSTITUTED phenylethylamines are possible precursors of some alkaloids and their occurrence in living plants, although in small quantities, is expected¹. Mass spectrometry is a very useful technique for the characterisation of these compounds, particularly in crude plant materials² and biological fluids^{3,4}. The relative merits and demerits of the different ionisation techniques as applied to the identification of these compounds have not been studied so far. We report in the present communication the synthesis of substituted phenylethylamines (4-10) and the corresponding Schiff bases (11-17), and a comparative study of their positive and negative ion mass spectra.

borohydride followed by hydrogenolysis with hydrochloric acid finally gave the desired substituted phenylethylamines (4-10) (Scheme 1). The ir, uv, pmr and the elemental analysis of the compounds were in conformity with the assigned structure.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
4	-CH ₃	-	H	Bz	11	-CH ₃	-	H	Bz
5	Me	Me	H	Bz	12	Me	Me	H	Bz
6	Me	Bz	H	Me	13	Me	Bz	H	Me
7	Me	Me	OBz	Me	14	Me	Me	OBz	Me
8	Me	Bz	OMe	Me	15	Me	Bz	OMe	Me
9	Me	Bz	H	Bz	16	Me	Bz	H	Bz
10	Me	Bz	OBz	Me	17	Me	Bz	OBz	Me

Scheme 1

Mass spectra: The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol-D300 mass spectrometer having a JMA-2000 data system. The samples were introduced through the direct inlet system and heated to 150-200°. The CI(NH₃) spectra were recorded at a source housing pressure of 1.5 × 10⁻⁵ torr; the other ion source conditions being electron energy, 70 eV (EI), 200 eV (CI); emission current, 100 μA (EI, positive), 300 μA (EI, negative and CI, positive); temperature, 200°. The metastable spectra were recorded on a Jeol OISG-2 mass spectrometer using the high voltage scan technique⁵; the ion source

Experimental

Synthesis: Condensation of suitably substituted phenylethylamines (1) with suitably substituted benzaldehydes (2) yielded the Schiff bases (3). Treatment on 3 with methyl iodide furnished the iminium salts which on reduction with sodium

[†] CDRI Communication no. 3696.

conditions being electron energy, 75 eV ; emission current, 50 μ A ; temperature, 200°.

Results and Discussion

Phenylethylamines: The positive ion (EI and CI using NH_3) and negative ion (EI) mass spectra of 4–10 are given in Figs. 1 and 2, while the fragmentation pathways supported by metastable data and exact mass measurements are shown in Scheme 2. No $M^{+\cdot}$ could be detected in any of

Fig 1. Mass spectra of 4–6 (i-isotope peaks excluded).

Fig. 2. Mass spectra of 7–10 (isotope peaks excluded).

these compounds under EI conditions. Of the three possible benzylic cleavages (i–iii), only two processes (ii and iii) giving rise to tropylium ions 'c' and 'd' are important. Depending upon the substitution pattern these ions, 'c' and 'd' give rise to the base peaks in the spectra of 4–10. The only nitrogen containing fragment ion observed is the α -cleavage ion 'b'.

Scheme 2

The $^3\text{Cl}(\text{NH}_3)$ spectra, however, give the molecular protonated ion as the base peak thus enabling the unambiguous determination of the molecular weight. Intense peaks corresponding to ions 'b' and 'c' are also observed under CI conditions. The CI spectra of 4–10 also show a peak at m/z value higher than that of MH^+ . It is interesting to note that this ion at m/z 572 in 4 appears to be formed by the addition of ion 'c' (benzyl form) to the neutral molecule resulting in the quaternary ion $(M+c)^+$. This is further supported by the corresponding shift in the m/z value of this ion in the differently substituted compounds. Attachment of tropylium ion to organic sulphur compounds under CI conditions has recently been observed by Hill⁸ who suggested this as a method for the selective analysis of organosulphur compounds. However, the present results indicate that tropylium ion adducts can be formed in other classes of compounds as well.

The negative ion spectra of 4–10 show only the phenoxide ion resulting from the loss of a benzyl group and as such are of not much use in the identification of these compounds.

Schiff bases : Under electron impact Schiff bases normally fragment by loss of aryl groups followed by HCN or ArCN⁻⁹. However, in the spectra of the Schiff bases derived from substituted phenylethylamines the corresponding ion 'e' formed by the loss of benzyl group does not lose HCN. The fragment ions observed in the spectra of 11–17 correspond to the tropylium ions 'a' and 'd' (Scheme 2).

TABLE 1—ION ABUNDANCES (%) IN THE ELECTRON IMPACT SPECTRA OF 11–17

Compd.	Ion			
	M ⁺	a	d	e
11	359 (11.1)	135 (30.0)	91 (100)	224 (93.4)
12	375 (10.5)	151 (17.0)	91 (100)	224 (65.0)
13	375 (20.9)	227 (4.0)	91 (73.5)	148 (100)
14	405 (10.7)	151 (36.0)	91 (100)	254 (24.4)
15	405 (17.4)	227 (4.0)	91 (65.7)	178 (100)
16	451 (3.6)	267 (9.0)	91 (100)	224 (20.7)
17	481 (8.5)	211 (1.0)	91 (100)	254 (34.3)

Measurable molecular ion peaks are also observed (Table 1). Thus, their EI behaviour is similar to that of the phenylethylamines described above. Only MH⁺ and (M–Bz)⁻ ions are observed in their positive ion CI (NH₃) and negative ion EI spectra, respectively.

This comparative study reveals that positive ion chemical ionisation technique is a better choice than electron impact ionisation (both positive and negative) for the identification of phenylethylamine derivatives, while electron impact ionisation is to be preferred for the identification of their Schiff bases.

Acknowledgement

Grateful acknowledgement is made to R.S.I.C., Lucknow, where the mass spectral studies were carried out.

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